

Spectrophotometric Determination of Nickel(II) after Adsorption of its Complex with 2-(Naphthalidine)pyridine on Polyurethane Foam

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The present communication describes an inexpensive, accurate, reproducible, selective and sensitive method for the photometric determination of nickel(II) with 2-(naphthalidine)pyridine. The effects of pH, reagent concentration, adsorbent, shaking time and diverse metal ions on absorbance studies have been investigated. Conditions have been optimized for the determination of Ni^{II} in alloys.

Schiff's bases are considered as potent reagents for the determination of a number of metal ions^{1,2}. Diverse methods for the spectrophotometric determination of nickel(II) have been reported earlier.

In the present study, a new method of extraction 'solid-liquid extraction' as modified by Bowen⁴ using polyurethane foam (commercial U-foam) as an adsorbent has been used for the photometric determination of Ni^{II} with 2-(naphthalidine)pyridine (SB₁). The use of polyurethane foam in extraction study offers low solubility of the extractant, easy use of large phase ratios, easy separation of phases and a synergistic extraction effect. This method is very convenient and less time-consuming. The Ni^{II}-SB₁ complex has been rapidly adsorbed on polyurethane foam which has then been eluted from foam pieces by squeezing with chloroform. The absorbance of the solution is measured at 435 nm against reagent blank.

Results and Discussion

Nickel(II) complex with SB₁ was obtained from the sample solution containing 60 µg of Ni^{II} and 0.2% reagent solution (2.0 ml) at pH 3.0 according to the recommended procedure. For complete adsorption of the complex, five foam pieces were found to be enough. The shaking period of 180 s was found to be sufficient enough for complete adsorption of the metal complex on foam pieces. Ten samples of the solution containing 60 µg of Ni^{II} were prepared by the recommended procedure, providing a mean absorbance of 0.576 with a relative standard deviation of 0.46%. Beer's law was obeyed over the concentration range 10–100 µg of nickel(II) in 10 ml chloroform. The molar absorptivity at 435 nm was found to be 3.01 × 10⁴ dm³ mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹ and sensitivity being 0.0104 µg cm⁻² of nickel(II) for 0.001 absorbance. The effect of addition of diverse metal ions was investigated. It was observed that in lower concentration there was no appreciable interference, but at higher concentration they interfered. The tolerance limits (in µg given in parenthesis) are as follows: Ag^I, Co^{II}, Cu^{II}, Fe^{III}, Cr^{III}, Pt^{IV} and U^{VI} (100); Pd^{II}, Mn^{II} and V^V (160).

The results of determination of Ni^{II} in alloy samples are presented in Table 1.

TABLE I—DETERMINATION OF NICKEL(II) IN ALLOYS

Sample Composition %	Ni ^{II} (µg)		Average µg	Error %
	Taken	Found		
Stainless steel 304 (Cr, 18.0; Ni, 8.12; Fe, 70–71)	60.00	59.50	59.76	+0.40
		60.02		
		59.77		
		59.75		
Stainless steel 316 (Cr, 16.5; Ni, 12.0; Mo, 2–3)	60.00	59.52	59.80	+0.33
		60.11		
		59.59		
		60.00		

Experimental

A standard stock solution (100 µg of Ni^{II}) was prepared by dissolving nickel nitrate in distilled water and further diluted to get 1 µg of standard solution of Ni^{II}. A 0.2% solution of 2-(naphthalidine)pyridine was prepared in ethanol. Buffer solution (pH 3.0) was prepared by mixing equal volume of 1 M acetic acid and 1 M ammonium acetate.

All chemicals used were of spectrograde quality. A GS 5701 EC spectrophotometer and a Systronics 335 pH meter were used.

Procedure: Polyurethane foam (commercial U-foam) pieces were taken and prepared by the reported method⁵. A few uniformly sized (about 1 cm³) foam pieces were soaked in 1 M HCl for 10–12 h for removal of possible inorganic contaminants. The pieces were rinsed thoroughly with distilled water, squeezed and dried in air. The polymeric properties were found to remain intact as a result of these treatments. The foam pieces were then ready to be used.

To an aliquot (2.0 ml) of standard Ni^{II} solution, a 0.2% reagent solution (2.0 ml) was added and the pH adjusted to 3.0 using the acetate buffer solution. The solution was made upto 10 ml using distilled water and allowed to stand for 180 s for complete development of color. Five prepared polyurethane foam pieces were added to it and shaken vigorously for 180 s to ensure complete adsorption of the

metal complex on the foam pieces. The foam pieces were then squeezed and traces of reagent were further squeezed out. The complex was then eluted from foam pieces by squeezing with chloroform (2×5 ml). Traces of water were removed by adding anhydrous sodium sulphate. Finally, the absorbance was measured at 435 nm against reagent blank.

Determination of Ni^{II} in alloys : An alloy sample weighing 0.6 g was dissolved in requisite amount of aqua regia. The volume of the solution was reduced to 5 ml by evaporation. To it, concentrated HCl was added and warmed. The volume of the resultant solution was made upto 250 ml using distilled water. An aliquot of the solution was boiled for a few minutes, cooled and the pH adjusted to the optimum value. The results are depicted in Table 1.

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